

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R9.12 Czech-Norwegian CCS workshop held in Norway

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1 INTRODUCTION

In order further to promote and strengthen mutual Czech-Norwegian cooperation in the area of CCS, a Czech-Norwegian CCS Research Workshop was organized on June 19th, 2023 in Scandic Lerkendal Hotel in Trondheim, Norway. At the same week, the Trondheim CCS-12 Conference was held, so we use the possibility to combine our workshop and conference, saving project travel budget.

The half-day workshop included a presentation of the Czech-Norwegian CCS projects, and offered ample space for discussions and networking between Czech and Norwegian experts. The following participants took part in the workshop: Juraj Franců, Petr Jirman, Eva Hudečková (CGS), Anders Nermoen, Eric Patrick Ford (NORCE), Vladimír Opletal and Jiří Gavor (MND).

2 DISCUSSION TOPICS

1. **Dynamic model** will use gridding with **follow base layering** because it is more geological. Anisotropic distribution of porosity and permeability will be used in the Gaussian gridding simulation (statistical distribution of property).

2. **Fracture modelling** will be used for detailed definition of petrophysical properties.

3. Final **distribution petrophysical properties** will be modified in **ECLIPSE** environment (Milan Pagáč) to fit the **history matching** related to production from all used wells (input from static model will not be modified in order to preserve reproducibility of model building).

4. Next step – simulate the future CO₂ injection to the storage.

5. Scenarios – **Injection well** – preferentially ZA7, while ZA3 used as **monitoring** well (P-T conditions). Alternative scenarios of injection through ZA3 and ZA7 may be modelled to compare the resulting process (if possible).

6. **How much CO₂** are we planning to store? According to EU = CZ legislation: Pilot = maximum 100 000 tons of CO₂. For safety reasons 70 000 tons CO₂ are planned.

7. **Timing: 2 years** with periodical injections at 5,6 kg/s storage rate (truck comes a downloads 20 t CO₂ in e.g. half an hour). Alternatively – 10 years.

8. **Storage rate** x 1000 tons/year

9. **EOR** yes or no? Legislatively not possible? This is a pilot where experiments are needed to find out new technologies. This is a different situation from everyday business legislation.

10. **Financial aspects** – Value Chain. First Pilot needs special extra funding.

11a. New **fibre glass tubing** will be installed during workover in **ZA7** in **Sep-Oct 2023**, downhole **gauge for pressure measurement** will be installed in ZA7 to be used in step-rate-test in October 2023 as part of the well log integrity experiment. **Monitoring by down hole pressure gauge** – should be easy to install, but survives only for a short time.

11b. Step-rate-test induced seismicity monitoring = issues – additional funding + availability of the seismic stations from the Geophysical institute of the Czech academy of Science (Petr Kolář)

12. We all need more details of the **geochemical CO₂-brine-rock interaction model**, preferably spatial (2D or 3D). Monika Ličbinská and Martin Klempa (VSB) will be asked to send the requested information to all team partners as soon as possible.

To summarize the conclusions of the workshop, homework was formulated for each participant.

Fig. 1-1: Photos from the Czech-Norwegian CCS Research Workshop held in Trondheim, June 19th, 2023.

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More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

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